

Consejos para la creación de pósters

Nicolás Guarín-Zapata

23 de abril de 2021

Los pósters son principalmente medios visuales usados para mostrar los puntos más importantes de un tópico. En el contexto de algunos cursos universitarios, pretenden servir como material de apoyo para la presentación de los proyectos de materia. Un póster efectivo presenta su proyecto y a su equipo de trabajo de forma clara y profesional, también fomenta la discusión de la audiencia con los presentadores.

Tenga en cuenta los siguientes consejos (The Pennsylvania State University, 2005):

- Conozca a su público para que pueda comunicarse con ellos de manera efectiva.
- El texto debe ser lo suficientemente grande como para ser visto desde 2 metros de distancia.
- La información debe organizarse de forma que guíe al espectador a través del póster.
- Hacer ilustraciones simples y llamativas.
- El póster debe ser autoexplicativo para que pueda hablar libremente.
- Mantenga los pósters simples y el texto breve; un espectador debe "entenderlo" en 30 segundos. Puede proporcionar información detallada en un folleto.

- Un póster de colores neutros en un tablero mate es más agradable a la vista que uno sobre un fondo de colores brillantes.
- Organice su material y edite su contenido para eliminar el ruido visual que distrae. En caso de duda, edite; asegúrese de que cada elemento es necesario.
- Tenga a la mano libreta y bolígrafos para notas, chinchas adicionales, alfileres, cinta adhesiva o pegamento.

Planeación

Uno de los aspectos más importantes antes de iniciar es conocer cuál será la audiencia y cuál es el mensaje que se quiere transmitir a esta. Un buen ejercicio es listar cuáles son los puntos más relevantes y centrarse en los tres o cuatro más importantes de esta lista. Una pregunta que vale la pena preguntarse es si una persona pudiera recordar una sola cosa, ¿cuál quisiera usted que fuera? (The Pennsylvania State University, 2005).

Estructura

Tamaño del póster: Supongamos un tamaño A0, $841 \times 1189 \text{ mm}^2$ ($33.1 \times 46.8 \text{ in}^2$)

Antes de iniciar el proceso en algún software (como PowerPoint) esboce la estructura usando lápiz y papel. Dos estructuras comunes son (Rowe, 2017):

- Estructura lineal, en donde se presenta la información de forma secuencial como siguiendo una “historia” (ver figura 1).
- Estructura satelital, en donde los elementos que conforman el póster giran alrededor de un núcleo o elemento más importante (ver figura 2).

Adicionalmente, la orientación del póster puede ser horizontal o vertical y la distribución de los elementos puede variar en cada caso.

Figura 1. Estructura de póster lineal (Rowe, 2017)

Figura 2. Estructura de póster satelital (Rowe, 2017)

Una estructura que es común en los pósters académicos/científicos consta de las siguientes secciones (IMRD):

- Introducción
- Métodos

- Resultados
- Discusión/Conclusiones

Estas secciones suelen estar presentes en artículos y por tanto se ha adoptado también en pósters. Este puede ser un buen punto de partida, sin embargo puede resultar un poco rígido ceñirse a este formato. La figura 3 presenta una primera etapa del póster ejemplo.

Figura 3. Primer esbozo sobre la estructura del póster hecha en una hoja de papel

Ejecución

A continuación se presentan algunos detalles respecto a la realización del póster.

Texto

Debido al amplio uso de la estructura IMRD, descrita anteriormente, es común que algunos pósters estén cargados de texto. Sin embargo, el póster no está pensado para ser un medio autocontenido, es decir, este existe como material de apoyo a la presentación/discusión y por tanto no se debe abusar de la cantidad de texto.

La tabla 1, presenta diferentes tamaños de letra recomendados para diferentes elementos de los pósters. Una buena práctica es fijar el tamaño de letra de cada sección de antemano, de tal forma que no exista la tentación de ubicar más texto del necesario.

Tabla 1. Tamaños de letra desde la perspectiva del espectador (Rowe, 2017)

Transeúnte 4 m Necesita ser atraído	80 – 40 Títulos
Espectador potencial 3 m Debe ser capaz de ver el título completo y quedar “enganchado”	≥40 24 – 28 Títulos Encabezados

<p>Espectador activo 1 – 2 m Debe ser capaz de leer todo el texto del póster</p>	<p>24 – 28 14 – 18</p> <p>Encabezados Texto</p>
---	--

Gráficos

Para facilitar el entendimiento es común hacer uso de diagramas y esquemas. Trate de usar gráficos de buena calidad. Tenga en cuenta las siguientes recomendaciones respecto a formatos de archivos:

- **JPEG:** debe ser usado únicamente para fotografías.
- **PNG:** es el formato sugerido para esquemas, diagramas y gráficos.

En ambos casos utilice imágenes de una resolución mínima de 150 ppp (puntos por pulgada), para esto tenga en cuenta el tamaño que la imagen ocupará en el póster. Por ejemplo, tomemos una imagen de $6 \times 3 \text{ in}^2$. Esta imagen tendría un tamaño (a 150 ppp) de 900×450 píxeles.

El siguiente bloque de código de Python crea una figura de $6 \times 3 \text{ in}^2$, realiza el gráfico de la función $f(x) = \sin(x^2)$ y lo guarda en una figura de 900×450 píxeles.

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

x = np.linspace(0, 2*np.pi, 500)
y = np.sin(x**2)
plt.figure(figsize=(6, 3))
plt.plot(x, y)
plt.savefig("figura_ejemplo.png", dpi=150)
```

Código 1. Ejemplo de Python para guardar figuras con el tamaño deseado

La figura 4 muestra el resultado obtenido con el bloque de código 1.

Figura 4. Gráfico generado con el bloque de código 1

Software

Existen diversas aplicaciones usadas para la creación de pósters. La más común de estas sería PowerPoint, o su equivalente libre LibreOffice Impress. El ejemplo fue creado usando LibreOffice Impress, pero pudo haberse hecho de igual manera con PowerPoint.

A continuación se presenta una lista de programas comúnmente usados en la creación de pósters.

Programas para presentaciones

- Microsoft PowerPoint
- LibreOffice Impress

Programas profesionales de diagramación

- Adobe InDesign
- Scribus

Programas de gráficos vectoriales

- Adobe Illustrator
- Inkscape

Adicionalmente también es común que se use LaTeX para la creación de pósters.

Iteración

Un aspecto clave para obtener un resultado satisfactorio es el de ir mejorando de forma incremental el diseño del póster. De esta manera puede verse qué aspectos funcionan y cuáles hacen falta para mejorar el póster.

Las figuras 5 y 6 presentan diferentes etapas en la creación del póster ejemplo.

Figura 5. Dos etapas (iniciales) en la creación de un póster

Figura 6. Dos etapas (finales) en la creación de un póster

Ejemplos

Se sugiere consultar la siguiente cibergrafía:

- [Behance]. Scientific Poster [Publicación de Pinterest]. Fecha de acceso: octubre 4, 2018. Disponible en: <https://co.pinterest.com/pin/438678819937613141/>
- [lin]. Discover ideas about Conference Poster Template [Publicación de Pinterest]. Fecha de acceso: octubre 4, 2018. Disponible en: <https://co.pinterest.com/pin/101894010298224061/>
- [Yisela]. Respuesta a: “Examples of good academic poster design” [Respuesta en GraphicDesign/Stack Overflow]. Fecha de acceso: octubre 4, 2018. Disponible en: <https://graphicdesign.stackexchange.com/a/9458/42659>
- Zen Faulkes (2015). In search of simplicity, plus a makeover [Entrada del blog Better Posters]. Fecha de acceso: noviembre 8, 2019. Disponible en: <https://betterposters.blogspot.com/2015/02/in-search-of-simplicity-plus-makeover.html>

A continuación se presentan algunos ejemplos.

Developing and characterising a novel combined nanoelectrode system

L. P. Robinson, A. Mount

Electrochemistry at nanoelectrodes

Nanoelectrodes have several advantages for electrochemical sensing. Transport to nanoelectrodes proceeds through a relatively efficient linear diffusion profile. They are also highly affected by convection and IR drop.

In contrast, the diffusion pattern for nanoelectrodes quickly becomes hemispherical. They are much more efficient, and they are not as affected by convection or IR drop. They can reliably detect very low (sub-nM) concentrations of analyte.

Ag/AgCl as a combined electrode

The combined reference/counter electrode is created by electrodepositing a thin film of Ag onto the Pt microarray.

Electrodeposition causes Ag to grow preferentially at the corners, creating dendrites. A galvanostatic plating protocol is being developed to provide the required smooth, shiny Ag deposit.

To convert the newly plated Ag surface to AgCl, it must be functionalised. Chemical functionalisation by immersion in KCl, has been shown to produce uniform deposits of AgCl.

Combined nanoelectrode system

The design consists of a microarray of the location of each cavity in the array, with the nanoband around the cavity edge.

The Ag/AgCl microarray is a combined reference and counter electrode. As it acts to much larger than the Pt nanoband, the current from the Ag/AgCl is not large enough to affect the Pt or the reference electrode.

This could create an on-chip device for sensitive analytical detection.

Fabrication

This design has been fabricated at the Scottish Microelectronics Centre using photolithography. In this technique layers of metal and insulator are deposited and patterned to produce the desired arrangement.

1. Si wafer with oxide surface
2. Metal is then deposited and coated in a nitride passivation layer
3. Photolith layer is deposited and exposed to UV light through a patterned mask
4. Nitride is removed and pattern metal layer

Each layer is deposited and patterned sequentially. This approach reliably produces uniform electrodes cheaply and easily.

Characterisation

Cyclic voltammetry and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy will be used to verify that the system is behaving as predicted. The nanoband should have a similar response to the current nanoelectrode array.

Example of a nanoelectrode cycling (100mV KCl) solution. This cycle used reference electrode of the electrode.

An application

By coating the surface of the working electrode in a porous conductive material, the corresponding DNA sequence can be detected using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Before the target is hybridised, the resistance measured for the redox couple is small. When the correct target is hybridised the resistance, and therefore the EIS response, is much larger.

The hybridisation, the redox couple is used for the electrode.

First hybridisation, the access of the redox species is restricted, and so the resistance rises.

EIS measurement of DNA electrode shows the increase in resistance upon addition of the target nucleic acid.

Objectives

Having made the initial measurements, the next steps will include:

- complete fabrication of the combined system, including optimisation of nanoband and cavity dimensions
- further investigation of the sensitivity of nanoelectrodes for use in DNA sensing and the relationship between the response and concentration of the target
- optimisation of a galvanostatic silver plating protocol

Many thanks to Dr Damien Corrigan, Ben Chalmers, Professor Andy Mount, the Mount group and the SMC for their continuing support and expertise.

SMC
SCOTTISH MICROELECTRONICS CENTRE

EPSRC
Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council

PERSONALITY, SEX DIFFERENCES, AND MATE CHOICE IN THE EUROPEAN SERIN

Ana V. Lattia & Paulo G. Mota

CEBQ Centro de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Recursos Genéticos, Universidade do Algarve, Laboratório de Ecologia, Coimbra, Portugal
*Corresponding Author: emota@uevora.pt

INTRODUCTION

- Animals can demonstrate individual behavioural traits that are consistent over time and in different contexts, also known as personality traits (Beebe et al., Philosophical Transactions R 2020).
- Personality has increasingly been the focus of ecological studies to understand the evolution and maintenance of these and its consequences.
- While several hypotheses have been considered, sexual selection has been scarcely studied although it is possible that it may play an important role in the origin and maintenance of personality differences (Schacht et al. Behaviour 2020).

OBJECTIVES

- Study consistent inter-individual differences in behaviour in the serin (Serinus serinus).
- Understand how sexes differ in their behavioural traits.
- Understand how different behavioural contexts are related and differ between sexes.
- Explore possible role of personality traits in female mate choice.

METHODS

- Wild serins (102 males and 17 females) were captured and maintained in an indoor aviary until the end of the experiment.
- Individuals were subjected to four behaviour tests to assess for (a) neophobia (b) sociability (c) and exploration (d), and tested for repeatable individual differences in two rounds.
- Mate choice tests were performed in an aviary (a) with a random female and a single combination of two males of similar colouration.

RESULTS

REPEATABILITY
Males and females differ in their consistency

Test	Personality
Neophobia	0.25
Sociability	0.18
Exploration	0.12

SEX DIFFERENCES
Males are more sociable than females (t=2.037, P<0.05)

MATE CHOICE
Female number of visits to males was related to their own personality trait (sociability) (r=0.485, p<0.05)

RELATIONSHIP ACROSS BEHAVIOURAL TRAITS
Personality and Mate Choice

CONCLUSIONS

- Individuals showed repeatability in the four behavioural tests.
- Males and females differed in their consistency and behaviour in their responses across the different tests.
- Behavioural traits were correlated, evidence of a possible behavioural syndrome, but differed between females and males. More sociable males were also more sociable, and females that were more sociable were less fearful and more easily less explorative.
- Mate choice tests, female personality was related with its own behaviour performance.
- Our results stress the importance of looking for sex differences in personality, and for considering the influence of personality in mate choice context.

A SHARED PROPENSITY TOWARDS FOOD AND ALCOHOL

Patricia N. Darmoko, Jenna R. Cummings, A. Janet Tomiyama
University of California, Los Angeles

BACKGROUND

Overeating and binge drinking are two of the most common health problems among college students. 48% students reported binge-eating symptoms. 63% females and 62% males had binge drinking episodes.

Most research examines the two problems in isolation, but food and alcohol might be more related than we realize.

Is alcohol similar to food?
Alcohol is derived from sugar (similar chemical bases with food). Both eating and drinking alcohol activate **appetitive pathways**. Addiction models have been applied to both food and alcohol use. Correlations between food and alcohol intake in animal studies?

Eating and drinking behaviors are highly driven by one's expectancies of food and alcohol. The more positive expectancies one has about the psychological effects of food and alcohol, the higher their consumption of food and alcohol respectively.

Since eating and drinking share similar biological pathways, could they also share similar psychological pathways?

MEASURES

ALCOHOL EXPECTANCY QUESTIONNAIRE (AEQ)

36-item questionnaire measuring one's anticipatory effects of drinking alcohol

Relaxation and Tension Reduction ("I feel relaxed, less nervous, less tense")

Annoyance and Aggression ("I feel annoyed, irritated, or angry")

Increased Social Assertiveness ("A few drinks makes it easier to talk to people")

Physical and Social Pleasure ("Having a drink makes me feel good")

Global Positive Changes ("I feel better overall")

Social Enhancement ("I feel that social life has had a number of benefits")

DUTCH EATING BEHAVIOR QUESTIONNAIRE (DEBQ)

26-item questionnaire assessing one's eating behaviors (since expectancies predict consumption), food expectancies are implicitly implied.

Emotional Eating: sensitivity to anticipated conformity benefits of eating ("I eat more when I am close to my friends with")

Emotional Eating: sensitivity to anticipated emotional benefits of eating ("I eat more when I am upset or depressed or disappointed")

CONCLUSIONS

DEBQ External Eating scale was correlated to all AEQ scales, while DEBQ Emotional Eating scale was only correlated to same, but not all, AEQ scales. This showed that:

External eating had a more consistent relationship with alcohol expectancies. We speculated that **impulsivity**, which is defined as tendency to act without adequate thought, might be implicated in both external eating and drinking behavior.

Emotional eating had a less consistent relationship with alcohol expectancies. We speculated that **depressive symptoms** are more highly associated with sensitivities to food than to alcohol.

AEQ Relaxation and Tension Reduction and AEQ Annoyance and Aggression had the highest correlations with DEBQ scales. We inferred that the **anticipatory psychological effects of alcohol are strongly associated to those of food.**

Non-significant correlations between DEBQ Emotional Eating scales and AEQ increased Social Assertiveness and AEQ Social and Physical Pleasure might imply that **social factors driving eating and drinking alcohol use might be less associated.**

In general, the results support our hypothesis that **food expectancy is positively correlated to alcohol expectancy.**

Intervention efforts for overeating and binge drinking among college students should thus consider the possibility that **addressing one of the two problems might directly or indirectly address the other.**

RESULTS

AEQ	DEBQ	External Eating	Emotional Eating
Relaxation and Tension Reduction	.316***	.239***	
Annoyance and Aggression	.244***	.223**	
Increased Social Assertiveness	.232***	.049	
Global Positive Changes	.226**	.027	
Social Enhancement	.224**	.168*	
Sexual Enhancement	.192**	.160*	

*p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001

METHOD

200 UCLA undergraduates (74% females; Mean age = 22.1) filled out an **online survey** in one sitting as part of a larger experimental study with the following **exclusionary criteria**:

- Less than 21 years old
- Self-reported history of eating disorders or substance abuse
- Absence from drinking beer
- A strict diet
- Food allergies to experimental stimuli

Food of propensity in English

REFERENCES

Altaba, L. (2013). Binge drinking and alcoholism: A developmental perspective. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 52(1), 1-11.

Altaba, L., & Volkow, N. D. (2013). Binge drinking and alcoholism: A developmental perspective. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 52(1), 1-11.

Altaba, L., & Volkow, N. D. (2013). Binge drinking and alcoholism: A developmental perspective. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 52(1), 1-11.

Figura 7. Ejemplos de pósters. El final de esta sección presenta enlaces a ejemplos.

Referencias

- Knaflig, C. N. (2015). *Storytelling with data: A data visualization guide for business professionals*. John Wiley & Sons.
- The Pennsylvania State University (2005). Designing Communications for a Poster Fair. Fecha de acceso: octubre 4, 2018. Disponible en:
<http://www.personal.psu.edu/drs18/postershow/>
- Rowe, N. (2017). *Academic & Scientific Poster Presentation*. Springer.